

Deperipheralisation of people and states in the algorithmic assemblage:
Court cases and a proposal for a new social contract

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Abstract

The article investigates what happens in the *platform economy* from the point of view of the algorithm-mediated relations established between corporations, governments, and users. From an assemblage approach, the article argues that a new order is emerging whose most salient feature is the collaborative alliances between governments and users versus the large corporations behind the platforms. A direct consequence of this is increasing regulation of platforms' economic activities. Based on the survey of four legal cases, the article applies a mapping method to identify the capacities exercised by the components of this algorithmic assemblage and observe that, while big tech corporations continue to occupy a central position, users and governments are pushing for the assemblage's reterritorialisation and, hence, their Deperipheralisation. Considering this novel trend, the article concludes that the most politically relevant pillar of the new identity of the algorithmic assemblage is a new social contract centred on data rights, literacy, and sovereignty.

Keywords: big data, assemblage, data regulation, Deperipheralisation, data literacy, data sovereignty

Introduction

With the digitalisation and datafication of everything, platforms dramatically affect public life and the social distribution of power and resources. Indeed, algorithmic systems can be designed for benign purposes, such as accelerating cancer detection (Nature Medicine 2019) and enhancing conservation (Adams 2019). Still, they can also be employed in manipulating democratic elections, and their biases can hurt the poor, strengthen racism, and intensify inequality (O’Neil 2016). Various forms of inequality (economic, political, cultural, or geographic) take on a particular hue in today’s datafied society.

In some cases, the algorithmic production of inequality has a clear spatial dimension. One case is the System Risk Indicator (SyRI) –an algorithmic alert system to detect welfare fraud in The Netherlands—whose biases helped perpetuate an exclusionary logic over poor neighbourhoods (Abu Elyounes 2021). In other cases, where a government does not mediate the relation between algorithm and user, living in central or peripheral locations marks a boundary on who has access to a service and who does not. For instance, Amazon’s Prime Free Same-Day Delivery service and pricing policies discriminate against minority districts in the US (Gralla 2016). In other cases, algorithms produce inequality with no apparent spatial translation. For example, studies show that high-income jobs are offered online to men more frequently than women (e.g., Datta, Tschantz, and Datta 2015). These unequal situations are possible because big data corporations have been given free rein to conduct their economic activities and gather data almost regardless of place. Only recently, regulations have been adopted to control this activity; but regulatory frameworks continue to face the *where* the problem (Rovatsos, Mittelstadt, and Koene 2020). Rulings are being issued

by national and international courts condemning large corporations for abusive practices in their platform services and advocating for the regulation of big data exploitation but are limited by their jurisdictions.

Here, we note that regulation is indicative that a new order is emerging in the socio-material system (i.e., in the *platform economy*) within which relations between users, corporations, and governments develop. We also note that an additional novelty is that the confluence of interests between governments and citizens/users against corporations' profit-driven interests is increasing. This is relevant because it highlights the capacity of different political sovereign units in the system to set limits on capital (here, on platforms) to guarantee the fundamental rights of users/citizens (Montalban, Frigant, and Jullien 2019).

The article examines the implications for power, politics, and space, following from the understanding that the platform economy is a complex geography of algorithm-mediated relations where each assembled entity defines its identity based on how it relates to others (DeLanda 2006). To this end, apart from Delanda (2006), we draw from Deleuzian theorists of multiplicity and heterogeneity whose work has inspired ways of thinking about power, politics, and space in human geography (Anderson and McFarlane 2011, Anderson, Kearnes, McFarlane, and Swanton 2012, Müller 2015, and Müller and Schurr 2016). In this vein, the article sets the concept of 'assemblage' (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987) as the primary heuristic tool to explore the socio-material system of relations mediated by algorithms. We do so in connection with four legal cases representative of the novel pattern pointed out before. Following an inductive strategy, we employ a mapping method to register the relations established between assembled entities in the four cases and catalogue them to observe a moment in the process of *deperipheralisation* of people and states. Namely, in these cases, we

detect that, by collaborating, governmental agencies and citizens undermine corporations or challenge their centrality.

Overall, in this article, we consider peripherality and centrality as conditions derived from processes of peripheralisation/centralisation that defy traditional centre-periphery thinking (Pugh and Dubois 2021). Still, it must be borne in mind that the platform economy rests on a distribution of roles across the globe that produces a particular economic geography. The platform economy is, therefore, actively engaged in the constitution of nationally and globally scaled centres and peripheries. While not the focus here, we can, for instance, think about the territorial anchor of *cloud computing*. Cloud computing –i.e., allowing remote servers to store, transfer, and process data globally— does not work in ether but from concrete locations. Amoore (2018, 4), indeed, admits that cloud computing has a ‘geographical character’ which concerns the spatial location of data farms and the analytic capacities of the cloud that render the invisible perceptible. Data farms are sometimes found in (semi-/)peripheral locations within the world economy (e.g., Yotta NM1, in Panvel, India) but belong to big tech companies headquartered in China and the US (Hosting Facts 2020). The companies behind these data farms are a mixture of publicly traded and private-owned firms, with little state intervention, except for one set up by the US National Security Agency in Utah, a peripheral territory in the US.

The article is structured as follows. The first section addresses the significance of platforms and algorithm-mediated relations for human geography. The second section elaborates on the potentialities associated with adopting a post-structuralist theoretical approach to think up the platform economy’s complex geography and the (de)peripheralisation processes operating within it. The third section provides clarification on the method and case selection. The fourth part presents the cases and

advances the categorisation of relations across assembled components in the algorithmic assemblage. The fifth part presents the reflections that arise from the cases about power, politics, and space. In the sixth part, we offer our conclusions. The authors generated the figures; the amounts are converted into euros using oanda¹.

Platforms in human geography

The platform economy has transformed consumption patterns, labour, urban planning, public services, and capital flows; new human geographies are also shaping in parallel.

Different authors are paying attention to varied aspects of the platform economy. For example, Ash, Kitchin, and Leszczynski (2016, 14) argue that geographers must continue critically thinking about geographic praxis while also employing the digital to generate knowledge since they are ‘ideally placed to map the socio-spatial materialities’ of the data regimes. These explorations include Thatcher’s, Burns’s, and Dalton’s (2021) study of the regional effects of algorithms and platforms and Kwan’s (2016, 274) analysis of the increased centrality of algorithms, introducing ‘more uncertainty to the geographic knowledge’ and influencing online research results. Novel interpersonal relationships and identity patterns around content publishing are coming to view, which Koch and Miles (2020) name ‘new geographies of encounter.’ Recently, Machen and Nost (2021, 564) examined climate knowledge production, signalling the hegemonising tendencies of algorithmic ways of thinking and calling for ‘a stronger critical research agenda around the limits of approaching climate decisions through algorithmic registers.’ Meanwhile, Van Doorn (2017) considers the gendered forms of control some

¹ <https://www1.oanda.com/lang/es/>

workers experience when performing paid tasks assigned by the platforms. And McNeill (2021) notes how algorithms shape urban spaces.

More relevant for this study is Richardson's attention to the cultural and performative dimension surrounding the 'sharing economy' and the kind of economic practices initiated around 'participation in the community and the division of its resources' (2015, 123). Richardson argues (2020) the study of the platform has emphasised it as either company or interface and algorithm. The first perspective of the platform as a profit-seeking company (Srnicsek 2017) derives from the immense wealth of the so-called platform economy, estimated at \$7 trillion. The platform economy is concentrated in a few hands and places. For example, it is ruled by conglomerates headquartered mainly in the US, accruing 4,157 million global users, or China, 3,792 million (Consultancy.org 2018). Meanwhile, one company –US-based Google— accounts for 86 percent of all Internet searches (Internet Live Stats 2015). The second idea of platforms as interfaces and algorithms is grounded on their capacity to monitor everyone connected to the platform anywhere, harvest their data, and transform them into information with spatial dimensions. Common to all platforms is that they do not generate their users' data (Craglia 2018).

Another relevant argument is that platforms operate as 'programmable spaces' in which the integration and distribution of its different elements rely upon 'logics of decentralisation and recentralisation' since the production of data occurs beyond the platform itself; still, data collected are recentralised to be monetised by the platform (Helmond 2015).

Platforms also benefit from the platform economy's 'unregulated spaces' and thrive in the intersection of the clashing forces of *collaboration* and *competition* driving it (Richardson 2020, 15). Looking at food delivery, Richardson concludes platforms are

more than just company or just algorithm since they can coordinate urban networks and generate ‘flexible spatial arrangements’ territorialised through a range of networked entities ‘beyond that of the interface and the algorithm’ (2020, 458).

Although Richardson does not adopt an openly Deleuzian perspective, this study expands her explorations of the platform as more than solely a company or an algorithm. Concretely, we observe how platforms such as Google and Facebook exert their collaborative or antagonising capacities to preserve their centrality in the algorithmic assemblage. We draw on Helmond’s idea of the recentralisation of data (2015) to think about an a-spatial centrality based on the corporations’ capacity to amalgamate data generated in the periphery of the algorithmic assemblage by users.

Post-structuralist geography and algorithm-mediated relations as ‘assemblage’

Power, politics, and space have received constant attention from human geographers. Until the mid-1980s, the discussions of power and politics were traditionally tied up to particular geographical scales and vertical conceptions of space (Marston, Jones III, and Woodward 2005). Behind this was the impulse to conceive local, urban, national, or global social relations as following a hierarchical pattern of spatial organisation. In this structuralist understanding, space pre-exists social action; social action is located within ‘contained spaces’ (Murdoch 2006), and notions of ‘centre’ and ‘periphery’ are used to pinpoint the hierarchisation of space within particular scales (Pugh and Dubois 2021).

What determines the condition of centrality in a space is that power and processes of economic accumulation concentrate ‘there’ at the expense of the peripheries occupying marginal positions (Pugh and Dubois 2021). This centre-periphery paradigm has nurtured rural/urban space analysis, emphasising the ‘co-existence of territorial extremes, from highly clustered to widely scattered milieux, on

all spatial scales' (Pugh and Dubois 2021, 272), and imposing a zero-sum logic to the understanding of space. In this paradigm, the *distance* of certain areas from the centre (i.e., topographical space) is a crucial generator of inequality and territorial imbalance in favour of urban centres. Yet, often little thought is given to how these territorial extremes come to be.

An alternative to traditional centre-periphery thinking is enabled when spaces are thought up as contingent and relational (Pugh and Dubois 2021, 271). Kühn (2015) uses the notion of *peripheralisation* to signal that neither peripheries nor centres are the natural forms in which space is organised and hierarchised but the product of social, political, and economic relations. Peripheralisation allows a process-centred perspective responsive to these relations' dynamism and the changing roles that space plays within systems (Kühn 2015, 369).

Peripheralisation can refer to exclusion from processes of capitalist accumulation, as in the theorisations of economic polarisation (Kühn 2015, 370); the marginalisation of social groups, emphasised in sociological approaches (Kühn 2015, 372); or the exclusion of groups or territories from power resources (Kühn 2015, 373). With this understanding of peripheralisation/centralisation, we can begin to weaken the logic of contained spaces. Still, one is not yet fully equipped to account for what goes on in *open spaces* like the platform economy. The problem is that dependence on scalar and structuralist thinking remains when addressing the logic of inclusion and exclusion or marginalisation. Our aim is to suggest that thinking up peripheralisation and centralisation processes without a scale (Marston, Jones III, and Woodward 2005) requires shifting attention from the container of social action (which ultimately is only a fiction) to those acting. But to do so, we need a post-structuralist geographical approach.

Here, we draw on the Deleuzian concept of assemblage (Deleuze and Guattari 1987) to explore ‘what goes on’ in the platform economy. The idea of assemblage has enjoyed substantial attention from human geographers (Müller 2015; Müller and Schurr 2016). The assemblage allows us to devise socio-material systems as wholes formed by different parts not hierarchically ordered, deal with the contingent stability of social forms, anticipate what is in the process of emerging, and, in sum, deal with the highly heterogeneous reality of the platform economy. Importantly, assemblage thinking focusses on the relations that bring parts together (Müller and Schurr 2016) and on the vulnerability to crises that characterises socio-spatial systems (Dittmer 2014, 394).

An essential interpreter of Deleuze’s and Guattari’s complex ideas, Manuel DeLanda (2006) notes that assemblages are historical wholes whose identity derives not from inherent properties but the capacities exercised by assembled components (DeLanda 2006, 10). In turn, the capacities of assembled components become visible as they enter associations with other components. DeLanda (2006, 12) also pinpoints that assembled components play material and expressive roles. In a border assemblage, for instance, walls, fences, and checkpoints physically limit human mobility (material components); meanwhile, the law expresses how mobility limitations shall be applied to nationals from different countries.

As they act, assembled components can territorialise or deterritorialise the assemblage (DeLanda 2006, 12). Territorialisation processes stabilise the assemblage’s identity, whereas deterritorialisation processes weaken an established identity (DeLanda 2006, 13). Thus, any process destabilising spatial boundaries or increasing internal heterogeneity is ‘considered deterritorialising’ (DeLanda 2006, 13). Relative to how territorialisation and deterritorialisation can be articulated, DeLanda (2006, 68-71) stresses the importance of coding and decoding capacities which, in turn, rely on

specialised expressive media, such as laws. In our analysis, we consider that regulating the activity of corporations in the platform economy is indicative of how, by exercising a coding capacity, the users-government alliance seeks to deterritorialise the algorithmic assemblage and replace the old identity with a data rights-centred identity.

The argument that assemblage-based geography offers the advantage that it ‘does not point to any particular spatial imaginary’ (Anderson, Kearnes, McFarlane, and Swanton 2012, 172) fits a strong commitment in this article: to understand ‘what goes on’ in the platform economy and the implications on power, politics, and space without falling into scalar traps (Marston, Jones III and Woodward 2005).

An assemblage-based geography (Anderson and McFarlane 2011, 125) is also particularly apt to grasp processes that are understood as ‘provisory’ and to find ‘new ways of conceptualising power and space’ (Dittmer 2014, 29); for instance, as ‘multiple coexistence’ (Anderson and McFarlane 2011, 125). On this, Bennett (2005, 445) notes that since no one member has sufficient competence to determine the assemblage activities, power cannot be an absolute asset. In the platform economy, it can be argued that big tech corporations take the lead in capitalist accumulation (Montalban, Frigant, and Jullien 2019). Still, they would not run full-fledged activities without users’ and governments’ collaboration. The political question is whether the terms and consequences of collaboration are entirely known to users and compatible with democratic public values (van Dijck 2020).

Adopting an assemblage approach makes us rethink power and its spatial enactments (Allen 1999). It takes us closer to an ‘immanent’ vision of power, understood as a ‘topological arrangement [...] where there are no predefined distances or simple proximities to speak of’ (Allen 2003, 19).

In sum, an assemblage approach helps us to map an emergent pattern of relations between corporations, states, and users and ponder over the possibilities of ‘political engagement’ (Allen 2004, 29) of heterogeneous actors in an algorithmic-mediated globalised economy that has ‘no outside’ (Allen 2003, 104).

Methods and case selection

Three types of assembled components are relevant to our analysis. The first type is states, understood for our purposes as an assortment of overlapping public entities endowed with regulatory capacities. National and international courts and any governmental body entitled to regulate are included in this type. The second type consists of the big tech corporations behind the platforms. The third type contains citizens/users and civil society groups.

The article seeks to understand what goes on in the platform economy by looking at assembled components and mapping their different capacities to fathom how they affect the assemblage, either stabilising or destabilising it. As the corporations’ dominant position has historically defined the platform economy, we assume that any action initiated by peripheralised components seeking to challenge that position aims at deterritorialising the assemblage, thus creating a new identity around previously neglected priorities (i.e., data rights).

Our mapping method consists in identifying capacities and their relational trajectories. Based on the observation of the cases, we use an inductive strategy to list capacities that are, in turn, classified as ‘positive’ or ‘negative.’ The qualifiers ‘positive’ and ‘negative’ signal the enactment of a capacity or its absence, not moral judgements. Thus, negative capacities are pinpointed when a component could have acted but has

failed to do so; by contrast, a positive capacity is a capacity that has been *de facto* exercised.

We also look at a capacity's trajectory, indicating either antagonism (dark arrow) when used against another component or collaboration (white arrow) when used in favour of another component. A shades code is also applied to distinguish three components and two types of relations (Figure 1).

[Figure 1 about here]

The diagrams capture a moment in the algorithmic assemblage whose most salient feature is the alliance of citizens and governments against corporations. They foreground the trajectory of relations extant amongst the algorithmic components, and the distribution of collaborative and antagonising capacities across the assemblage. Diagrams aim to convey that power as 'capacity to affect' the assemblage materialises in a 'multiple coexistence' (Anderson and McFarlane 2011, 125). They present the novel alliance between citizens and governments, showcasing the assemblage's movement towards a new identity where traditionally peripheralised components (mostly users) are employing this capacity to reterritorialise the assemblage around 'data rights.' The diagrams are imperfect because they are not dynamic, diachronic, interactive, or three-dimensional.

Our sampling strategy is purposive. The four legal cases share that the corporation that runs a platform or application has been taken to court by users, civil society groups, or public entities. The cases have been selected based on their currency and the exhibition of the following criteria: a) the defendant is a platform or the entity behind a data-driven algorithmic application; b) the complainant represents public interests; and c) there is diversity in themes. The US and Europe are overrepresented, as

they have introduced advanced regulations allowing people to sue corporations because of big corporations' abuses.

Analysis: Deperipheralisation of states and individuals

There are court cases where the confluence of interests between states and platforms is visible, consistent with the concepts of the informational state (Braman 2006), computational politics (Tufekci 2014), and dataveillance (van Dijck 2014). An example in Spain is the request made by Civio (a non-profit organisation that monitors power) before the Transparency Council in 2018 to compel the Ministry of Ecological Transition to release the code behind an algorithmic scheme that allocated electricity social bonuses to vulnerable consumers (Civio 2019). The council offered information about the scheme's functions, but not the code, protected by intellectual property regulation despite being developed with public funding (Belmonte 2019). This instance shows that public entities collaborate with corporations in the algorithmic assemblage. In parallel, it also indicates that civic components (here, Civio) try to reterritorialise the assemblage to re-centre vulnerable electricity consumers.

A significant difference between the Civio case and the cases under analysis here is that the latter illustrate the decoupling of corporate and state interests. A signal of this trend was the decision in 2016 by a French regulatory body to instruct Google to remove search result listings to pages comprising harmful or incorrect information about a person (Zalnieriute 2020). The following year, Google created a geo-blocking feature that prevents European users from seeing delisted links, but it defied the verdict for other parts of the world. The EU's top court ruled in 2019 that Google does not need to offer this feature worldwide. This case was the birth of the *right to be forgotten*.

Algorithmic systems are testing the limits of rights, and increasingly, states are siding with citizens. The SyRI case mentioned in the introduction is one example. In Spain, Mercadona, a supermarket chain, has been barred from using facial recognition on its clients to identify thieves (Pérez 2021). In the US, Facebook has agreed to pay \$650 million to settle a year-long class-action lawsuit over using facial recognition to identify faces in photos (Morrison 2020). And class actions against big tech are sprouting across the US (Brandom 2020).

Individual v. La Opinión de Zaragoza

In 2017, the Spanish Constitutional Court confirmed prior rulings holding *La Opinión de Zamora*, a newspaper, violating the data protection regulation when it published a picture of a Facebook user in 2013 (Diario Constitucional 2020). The newspaper appealed the ruling, arguing that the use of the image was motivated by the right to information. The court rejected the appeal and condemned *La Opinión de Zamora* because it had failed to request consent. Facebook's failure to grant protection to users' data rights enabled further violations of users' data rights by third parties.

The court's rationale was that the conditions of use in many platforms are a tangle of contractual clauses challenging access and understanding by the 'average user;' in contrast, the platform retains the possibility of modifying them without prior notice (Diario Constitucional 2020). According to the sentence, users and platforms enter an 'electronic contract,' but this relation is established under asymmetry conditions where users are denied the possibility of negotiating the contract provisions (BOE 2020, 27238). The ruling states that users are unaware that 'the information voluntarily provided is subject to a powerful exchange, processing, and analysis tools available to these platforms' (BOE 2020, 27238). The ruling defines users as 'collaborative subjects' in platforms, yet this collaboration occurs when the protection

of fundamental rights to honour, privacy, and image is not guaranteed (Diario Constitucional 2020).

Here Facebook exhibits several negative capacities: not granting by default protection to users (**protection capacity**), not making the terms and conditions of use intelligible (**literacy promotion capacity**), and not favouring the negotiation with users (**negotiation capacity**). Instead, Facebook exerts its capacity to **offer an online service** and benefit from unrestricted access to users' data (**data monetisation capacity**). Meanwhile, users feed the databases stored by the platform by sharing data and interacting with others (**feeding capacity**). They do this in a context of low awareness of the further circulation and processing of their data by the platform or third parties; namely, in conditions of poor **data literacy capacity**, and of **inability to negotiate** the legal terms under which the exchange occurs. Still, as Figure 2 shows, users' relation with the platform is collaborative.

[Figure 2 about here]

The case also shows that the Spanish Constitutional Court establishes a collaborative relation with users whose rights to image, privacy, and honour it seeks to protect. But it is antagonistic towards *La Opinión de Zamora*. The court sentenced the paper to repair the damage caused by disseminating the Facebook user's image without consent (**punitive capacity**). It is also antagonistic to Facebook as the court offers a critical assessment (**appraisal capacity**) of its regular *modus operandi*. Sentences are components of legal assemblages which play a vital expressive role in establishing correct and incorrect conduct. But legal pronouncements also play material roles in the assemblage, such as compensating the plaintiff with money. Despite the lack of punishment for Facebook, the sentence is expected to constrain the behaviour of third parties willing to employ platforms' content (Kernel Legal 2021).

FACUA v. LaLiga

The Spanish Professional Soccer League (known as LaLiga) was sentenced in 2018 to pay a €250,000 fine for lack of transparency when it exploited its app users' data to identify intellectual property infringements (Resolución de Procedimiento Sancionador 2018). The mobile application, which has about 10 million users, collected geolocation data and activated the microphone to detect bars where the app users gathered to check whether bars were licensed to show football matches (Moreno 2019)². The Spanish Data Protection Agency (SDPA) responded to a complaint issued by FACUA (an NGO that defends consumers' rights), which argued that recording ambient sound could capture conversations that may reveal the personal data of people who have not given their consent (Resolución... 2018). The SDPA also brought up issues regarding how consent is gathered from users.

LaLiga based its defence on technical arguments belittling the interference of these functionalities in the users' privacy and their acceptance of the app's terms and conditions of use. The main argument to defend the absence of intrusion through microphone activation is that the transformation of audio content into a digital fingerprint is 'unintelligible, irreproducible, and irreversible' (Resolución... 2018, 11-12).

LaLiga seeks to increase the detection of illegal broadcasting of football matches in bars (i.e., increase its **capacity to prosecute infringements**) through the collaboration granted by app users. Agreeing to collaborate here allows LaLiga app to run geolocation and sound recording functionalities (**surveillance capacity**). This collaboration protects teams and profits obtained from broadcasting licenses (**data**

² These functionalities are not available to the app users outside Spain.

monetisation capacity). The emergent capacity to appeal to users' emotions becomes the expressive means to encourage collaboration. Access to the app was preceded with the motto 'Protect your team!' In a sports environment with so many affective resonances, LaLiga brings to bear its **capacity to mobilise emotions** to fulfil its illegal broadcasting detection objectives. LaLiga declares not to pursue profit-making goals (Resolución... 2018, 17).

The SDPA imposed a fine on LaLiga, exercising its **punitive capacity**. The conditions under which users' consent is collected and the effects of functionalities like microphone activation on the right to privacy, intimacy, and secrecy of users' communications are the motives behind FACUA's complaint before the SDPA. The SDPA argued that the app collects consent from users regarding the activation of the microphone and geolocation functionalities (**capacity to obtain consent**), but only upon a first-time installation. The ruling identifies additional contentious points regarding compliance with the principle of transparency about the functioning of LaLiga app (**capacity to inform**). Once the **user has agreed** to the app's terms and conditions (**feeding capacity**), the app does not run reminders warning that these functionalities are activated. Transparency matters are addressed because users are unaware that the app is executed in the background with the microphone and geolocation functionalities running. The SDPA pinpoints that the app does not offer any visual sign indicating that these functionalities are active and that users' consent to microphone and geolocation functionalities can only be deactivated in the device's settings functions (Resolución... 2018). If, following Gutiérrez (2019), data literacy is the access to skills, tools, and opportunities to exercise data agency; it becomes evident that the app **does not offer users the opportunity to exercise such agential capacity**.

[Figure 3 about here]

As shown in Figure 3, a trajectory of antagonism connects FACUA with LaLiga, the SDPA with LaLiga, and LaLiga with bars. Relevant trajectories of collaboration have been addressed already, except for the one linking app users with bars. The point here is that soccer fans attend bars to watch matches. Thus, both parties benefit: LaLiga followers can gather around a football match, and bars profit from customers' consumption. Inadvertently though, customers who are also LaLiga app users place bars in the spotlight of inquiries.

Glawischnig-Piesczek v. Facebook

This case arose in 2016 when an anonymous Facebook user in Austria shared an abusive message against Austrian politician Eva Glawischnig-Piesczek. After attempting to get Facebook to remove the damaging content from the platform, Glawischnig-Piesczek appealed to the Vienna Commercial Court, which issued an injunction to eliminate the content. Facebook deactivated it only in Austria (Global Freedom of Expression 2019a). Both parties appealed to the Higher Regional Court, which referred to the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) questions about the geographic scope of the content's removal and the whereabouts of similar content posted by users different from the original. The CJEU concluded that existing directives do not prevent Member States (MS) from ordering a provider to remove information declared unlawful if they comply with international law (Global Freedom of Expression 2019a; see also, Judgement of the Court 3rd October 2019). MS cannot oblige platforms to monitor all hosted content but recalls the duty to act 'expeditiously' to remove or disable access to harmful content 'upon obtaining actual knowledge or awareness of illegal activity' (Recital 46 of Directive 2000/31/EC, Judgement of the Court 3rd October 2019).

This case offers insights into the platforms' capacity to act expeditiously to remove access to content that damages an individual's reputation (**capacity to act expeditiously**). Such capacity is not *ex officio* exercised by Facebook concerning the content held harmful to the reputation of Glawischnig-Piesczek. Failing to exercise this capacity, which would require monitoring the content posted on the platform, Facebook does not disrupt users' **feeding capacity**, avoiding hindering the collaborative relation it maintains with users.

Here we see that users also exercise the **capacity to disseminate harmful content** and their feeding capacity. The conflict between two rights comes into play: the right to free speech and not to have one's reputation damaged, as enshrined in the Austrian Civil Code. The case is an example of an individual's **capacity to seek the protection** of fundamental rights before national and European courts and **seek compensation**. We see a collaborative relation between the Austrian judicial bodies, the CJEU, and one individual. The relation between these judicial bodies and Facebook is antagonistic, but the **punitive capacity** is left to the national courts.

[Figure 4 about here]

The capacity of the courts to rule on competing rights is common to all cases (**capacity to rule on competing rights**) but is pertinent here. In its expressive role, the CJEU interprets that Directive 2000/31/EC does not prohibit MS from obliging hosting platforms to remove harmful content. Nor does it prevent them from ordering content blocking worldwide if their decisions follow international law and the principle of proportionality. Challenges to regulating platform activity lie here: in the complex balance of rights in the various national spheres and the field of international law. Significantly, forcing the platform to exercise greater vigilance over the content it stores

affects data traffic *qua* profits, challenging the corporations' core condition within the algorithmic assemblage.

New Mexico v. Google

At the time of writing, Google faces a lawsuit filed by New Mexico Attorney General Hector Balderas in February 2020, who alleges this company infringes on several school children's, educators,' and parents' privacy rights (Balderas 2020). The complaint pleads that Google collected sensitive information, such as locations, habits, contacts, passwords, and recordings, and used this information to supply its advertising business until 2014. The company has amassed these data in personalised profiles (Balderas 2020). The case illuminates what O'Neil (2016, 64) calls 'predatory' behaviour. Balderas already took Google to court in 2018 for violating child privacy regulation and is partaking in a broader antitrust investigation into Google, conducted by 50 state attorneys in the US in parallel with similar efforts by the US Department of Justice Federal Trade Commission (Statt 2020).

Through G Suite products for education (e.g., Gmail, Calendar, Drive) and Google Chromebook laptops, cloud content services company Google is installed at the core of New Mexico's education institutions. Google's capacity to exploit its unique position in the market (**capacity to offer a service and engage in monopolistic practices**) comes at the expense of extant laws, especially the Federal Children's Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA).

The capacities seen before are present; negligent practices are repeated, especially regarding data literacy and consent. The trajectory of collaboration between users and Google and the latter's profit-seeking goals sustains elements together in this whole. This relation is affected by the New Mexico chief legal officer's complaint seeking to bring Google to compliance with existing regulations (Balderas 2020, 3).

According to Balderas (2020), Google conducts spy activities on school children using the G Suit products without educators or parents being aware of its monitoring capacity and commercial purposes (**impeding data agency**). Google exercises its **surveillance capacity** and fails to **protect and promote data literacy**. It also fails to **act transparently**). This is worrying from a public interest viewpoint, considering the involvement of children under thirteen. COPPA was passed in 1998 to ensure parents' involvement in children's online activity. Yet, Google does not exercise its **capacity to obtain** 'verifiable parental **consent**' from New Mexican parents, which hampers their ability to review or limit the platform's handling of their children's data (Balderas 2020, 5).

[Figure 5 about here]

Here, the public interest advocacy role played by the New Mexico Attorney General is critical to building a collaborative relation with Google's users. The flip side is that Balderas' antagonism to Google's abusive practices is categorical. This is a case where Google's ability to monopolise a service and pursue private gains undermines the right to education and the non-exploitation of personal data. It tells us about the platforms' extraordinary capacity to affect the rest of the components. Students and their parents are 'powerless to refuse' education (Balderas 2020, 23); teachers are also 'victims' of Google's marketing practices (Balderas 2020, 5), and, behind the appearance of a free service, Google is creating 'future generations of consumers' (Balderas 2020, 14).

Discussion

Corporate capacity to affect the algorithmic assemblage outweighs state and people's capacities, but regulation curbs rampant profit-seeking

This article identifies state agencies and citizens collaborating to reterritorialise the algorithmic assemblage. These alliances are novel. In *Change of State* (2006), Braman talked about the emergence of the ‘informational state,’ whose frontiers are conceptual ‘border zones of varying width,’ expanding their reach, for example, when they can serve to justify US interventions elsewhere (Braman 2006, 318). The notion of ‘computational politics’ pursued by Tufekci referred to ‘applying computational methods to large datasets derived from online and offline data sources for conducting outreach, persuasion, and mobilization’ (Tufekci 2014). Computational politics depended on a public-private association. The concept of ‘dataveillance’ was used by van Dijck (2014) to point out the continuous scrutinising of people’s communications across various platforms providing financial, geolocation, and networking services. This monitoring was done thanks to a corporate collaboration with state intelligence agencies (van Dijck 2014, 1).

Theorisations around the informational state, computational politics, and dataveillance emphasised the state’s monitoring capacities in collusion with corporations. In the informational state, governments use the *panspectron* to monitor citizens, resulting in ‘a gap between the identity of the informational state as perceived by those in government and as perceived by citizens’ (Braman 2006, 315). In computational politics, political campaigns study voters while voters have ‘no idea’ of the campaign’s modelling schemes (Tufekci 2014). Computational politics are impenetrable, as they rely on opaque or black-box algorithms, which are ‘proprietary,’ ‘undisclosed,’ and ‘controlled’ by a few platforms (Tufekci 2014). Meanwhile, dataveillance is based on a government and industrial drive toward a massive gathering of personal data (van Dijck 2014, 201). The three concepts flagged that surveillance and manipulation were the main underlying drivers of data-based systems.

Until recently, techno-enthusiasm and the lack of appropriate regulation fuelled a dynamic of centralisation around the corporate pole. Public entities took advantage of corporations' services to pursue their agendas, failing to shield citizen rights from abusive profit-seeking practices. From this, it can be inferred that states have been instrumental to the dynamics of capitalist accumulation (Montalban, Frigant, and Jullien 2019). But the legal cases inspected here, although not statistically representative, offer the possibility of charting a trajectory that deviates from the dominant pattern of public-corporate association.

Corporate components accumulate more capacities in these cases and often exercise them negatively. The positive capacities they employ the most are the power to offer services, control, and monetise data. In contrast, they refrain from using their capacities to protect, promote data literacy, and obtain user consent. Public entities deploy the highest number of positive capacity applications: they prosecute infringements, use the punitive capacity, and act as guardians of the public interest. Sometimes they use their capacity to appraise, rule on competing rights, and constrain action. Although individuals and organised society retain the power to seek protection, offer their consent, and issue a complaint, they do not exercise their ability to negotiate the conditions in which they collaborate with platforms or exercise their data literacy.

Some states are issuing new compliance requirements by amending laws, enacting new legislation, and applying it to favour people. Notably, the European Union, which hosts only 18 percent of the platforms (Consultancy.org 2018) but is a vast platform market (European Commission 2021), has implemented the General Data Protection Regulation. European national data protection commissions are already investigating platforms for non-compliance. The rulings reviewed here endorse citizens' rights to data protection, image, privacy, honour, intimacy, and

information freedom. In the case of *Glawischnig-Piesczek v. Facebook*, this support is carried across three courts at national and international levels; in the *New Mexico v. Google*'s case, it is the state of New Mexico that takes Google to court.

This is not to say that states and individuals are out to destroy companies via enhanced and applied regulation. Although the platforms' position in the current regime is hegemonic, both states and citizens are integral parts of the assemblage. We do not see here a zero-sum game between corporations and users, nor do we consider it realistic to advocate the withdrawal of capital no matter what. This is consonant with the idea that economies are 'diverse formations that appear through and are driven by various passions, metaphors, and practices that cannot be reduced to individual/corporate competitiveness' (Richardson 2015, 121), and with power as capacities to affect assembled components in many ways.

This situation points to a need for increasing data activism, understood as campaigning, social action, and mobilisation around the data infrastructure, only possible if people have data literacy. Data activism can include *sousveillance* and resistance practices, or what Rodríguez-Pose calls 'the revenge of the places that don't matter' (Rodríguez-Pose 2017, 189). Considering the cases here, data literacy's definition could be understood as including people's abilities to a) understand the implications of consenting to data extraction and disseminating (harmful) private information, b) affect the algorithmic design and decision-making, c) negotiate the platform's terms of use, d) issue complaints, start legal actions, and seek legal protection from abusive behaviour, and e) organise collectively to scrutinise algorithms and extract and analyse data from platforms in their own terms. States can support data activism by, for instance, increasing their offering of open data, allowing access to code

bought with public money, or including citizens in algorithmic design and decision-making.

However, the future of these disruptive processes is uncertain. As Tufekci (2014) notes on previous technologies: ‘From the telegraph to the radio, the initial period of disruption was followed by a period of consolidation in which challengers were incorporated into transformed power structures, and disruption gave rise to entrenchment.’ Whether data activists will fall prey to co-optation remains to be seen. The cases examined here do not constitute an established trend, as the platforms’ corporations are still dominant.

The peripheralising effects of epistemological asymmetries: Towards a data rights-centred ‘social contract’ for the digital age

The platforms’ business model is based on the citizens’ inability to negotiate or change terms and conditions. Consenting to the platforms’ terms of use without fully understanding the rights’ assignment that the user makes to the corporation and the lack of transparency that characterises corporate practices call attention to the dynamics of exploitation and epistemological asymmetries that occur in the algorithmic assemblage (Baack 2015; Elwood 2007).

But the cases show users are necessary collaborators of the platform economy and the accumulation regime that enriches the big technology companies. From this point of view, users ‘have power.’ Of course, there is a difference between the cases in which a user’s voluntary action initiates collaboration (e.g., in LaLiga App case) and cases in which public entities mediate collaboration (e.g., learning platform enrolment of minors in New Mexico). Within our sample, *New Mexico v. Google* requires a careful reflection regarding the liability of state components that abandon the right to

education in the hands of platforms and educational institutions' dependence on cloud computing serviced by private corporations for profit-making.

One could ask whether the adult platform users would (and could) behave differently if they were fully aware of the enrichment and abuse generated by their 'I consent' routines, which is part of the platform user's performance (Richardson 2015). This is a relevant question that has implications for individual participation in processes of capitalist accumulation that generate and benefit from data. The response cannot be decided individually (e.g., refusing to download apps or platform-mediated compulsory education). If there is 'no outside' (Allen 2003, 104) to the platformised capitalist accumulation system, the possibility of change lies primarily in reforming the inside.

So, our survey draws attention to two lines of action. The first is more regulation. Self-restraint was left up to computing platforms at an initial stage of algorithmic enthusiasm; when the first consequences of monopolistic behaviour were evident, states started to change regulations and develop new laws. Looking at data protection, Bellanova (2017, 340) says that 'governing through data implies, first and foremost, governing data,' but this cannot be done only from a national perspective. New approaches to data storage and processing have broken down conventional political borders. Therefore, national legal infrastructures (including doctrine, procedures, and institutions developed in the 19th and 20th centuries) 'are not necessarily adept at protecting the liberty and equality values threatened by the new algorithmic capabilities' (IACL News 2019). The state's regulation capacity should exhibit flexibility towards the territorial scope of application. Regulation and other state incentives (from tax breaks to fines) could reverse the direction in which the big tech components apply their capacities, putting pressure on them to protect users, promote data literacy, and be transparent.

And the second is a new social contract for the digital age with data rights at the centre (van Dijck 2020). This is the most relevant political implication arising from the assemblage-based approach to the platform economy adopted here. Perhaps current levels of participation show that people are willing to relinquish data in exchange for the services provided by the platforms. The assemblage's state components must intercede not to make people more careful with the data they share but to increase their data literacy. As users occupy peripheral positions in the algorithmic assemblage, any capability meant for not compensating for these epistemological gaps further deepens their marginalisation.

Conclusions

This article has adopted an assemblage-based approach to discussing 'what goes on' in the platform economy. Indeed, what goes in the platform economy is much more than what we were able to address here. An *open space* that quintessentially represents diversity and heterogeneity, we have primarily envisaged the platform economy in terms of the relations that three types of assembled components (corporations, governments/public components, and users) establish with each other. By mapping the components' capacities to affect each other, we try to contribute to thinking about the (always contingent) conditions of centrality and peripherality that the platform economy favours in everyday spaces of algorithm-mediated social relations such as education, leisure, and communication.

In this regard, it is possible to conclude that the platformisation of social, political, and economic exchanges in the era of techno-capitalism occurs in relational spaces characterised by great asymmetries. These asymmetries include, notably, the epistemic disproportionateness that places platform users at a disadvantage vis-à-vis the

corporations that exploit their data, and the asymmetry implicit in the fact that, for citizens everywhere, it is not possible to defect from the datafication and platformisation processes that governments and private entities foster. This *lopsidedness* is not easily analysable within traditional centre-periphery analytics. Here, centrality and peripherality are functions of the assembled components' capacity to affect the whole. Namely, the functions associated with data literacy, regulation, or the monetisation of economic activities are not clear manifestations of topographical distance from territorialised economic or political power centres.

This does not preclude us from recognising that the production of territorial peripheries and cores (such as those associated with cloud computing and the localisation of data farms) are not relevant to understanding further the platform economy's participation in the production of the uneven spaces of techno-capitalism. Our attempt to look at what goes on in the platform economy without scale does not mean that the actual functioning of the platform economy is not geographically embedded. Here, we have foregrounded the space of (almost unlimited) possibilities that global markets represent for the economic activity of big technological corporations vs. spaces of legal application of regulations mirroring state-centred sovereignty paradigms. Avowedly, obstacles to the governance of the algorithmic assemblage come from the major geographical asymmetries existing between big tech's capacity to act across borders siphoning data, and the territorially bound legal principles that underpin regulation.

Notwithstanding, this general picture might be changing. First, some court rulings favouring people are having extraterritorial effects or are expected to have them. Cases like *Glawischnig-Piesczek v. Facebook*, quoted in another court case in the *Ramdev v. Facebook* case in India (Global Freedom of Expression 2019b), showed that

national courts can affect the business activity of platforms beyond the national context in which a case was initiated. And second, though not within the scope of this study, a process of *Internet territorialisation* is in the making (Gstrein 2020). The latter seeks to replicate territorial notions of national law in cyberspace. Again, the Internet's territorialisation penalises citizens 'who are denied access to services, information, and communication means, while big tech finds ways to bypass great digital walls' (Gutiérrez 2022). One example is Facebook, which generates 'meaningful revenue from a limited number of resellers representing advertisers based in China' (Facebook, Inc. 2020, 34), despite the Chinese Great Firewall.

Today, it is hard to imagine a platform economy regulated so that users' rights are placed above the logic of extraordinary profits. A democratically governed platforms-based economic order is not in sight, but it is not impossible. Whether the collaborative alliances between users and governments are enough to upset an algorithmic assemblage dominated by corporations thus far remains to be seen. Still, it is relevant that public entities and other social actors are breaking with the logic of pandering to corporate interests.

Disclosure statement

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